

Employees in Term Work for At least 5 Years in the Italian Regions

Istat calculates the amount of temporary workers for at least five years as a percentage of total jobs according to Istat data. Between 2004 and 2019 they decreased in the Italian regions, except in Abruzzo, Puglia, Liguria, and Molise.

The ranking of those employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years. Istat calculates the amount of temporary workers for at least 5 years as a percentage of total jobs. The data refer to 2019. Sicily is in first place with a value of 31.8%, followed by Puglia with a value of 25.9% followed by Calabria with a value of 23.7%. In the middle of the table there are Campania with a value of 18%, Liguria with a value of 16.6% and Emilia-Romagna with a value of 16.4%. Piedmont closes the ranking with a value of 11.8%, Veneto with a value of 10.7% and Lombardy with a value of 9.9%.

Ranking employed in fixed-term contracts for at least 5 years in the period between 2004-2019. It is possible to calculate the value of the difference in the value of those employed in fixed-term contracts for at least 5 years between 2004 and 2019 for the purpose of creating a ranking. Obviously, in this case, the best performing regions are the regions that have seen a reduction in the amount of the percentage of temporary workers for 5 years compared to the total number of employees. In first place there is Calabria which between 2004 and 2019 was characterized by a reduction in the value of temporary employees for at least 5 years equivalent to an amount of -16.2 units, followed by Campania with a value equal to - 8.3 units and from Basilicata with a value of -7.3 units. In the middle of the table there are Sardinia with a value of -3.2 units, Lazio with a value of -2.6 units and Emilia-Romagna with a value of -2.1 units. Puglia closes the ranking with a value of 1.2 units, followed by Liguria with a value of 1.7 units and Molise with a value of 6.2 units.

The trend in the percentage of temporary contract workers for at least 5 years in Northern Italy. The value of those employed in fixed-term work for at least 5 years decreased in Northern Italy between 2014 and 2019. In 2014 the value of those employed in fixed-term work for at least 5 years in the North was equal to a value of 15.2 units and remained at this amount also in 2015. Between 2015 and 2016 the value of those employed in temporary work for at least 5 years decreased from a value of 15.2 units to a value of 13.5 units or equal to an amount of -1.7 units equal to a value of -11.18%. Between 2016 and 2017 the value of those employed in fixed-term contracts for at least 5 years in the North decreased from a value of 13.5 units to a value of 13.3 units or equal to a value of -0, 2 units equal to -1.48%. Between 2017 and 2018, the value of temporary employees for at least 5 years decreased from a value of 13.3 units to a value of 12.6 units or equal to a value of -0.7 units equal to a value of -5.26%. Between 2018 and 2019, the value of temporary employees for at least 5 years remained constant at a value of 12.6 units. Overall, between 2014 and 2019 the value of those employed in 5-year fixed-term contracts in Northern Italy decreased by -2.6 units equal to a value of -17.11%.

The trend in the percentage of temporary contract workers for at least 5 years in Central Italy. The value of the percentage of workers with fixed-term contracts for at least 5 years in Central Italy was equal to a value of 19.2 units. Between 2014 and 2015 the amount of temporary contract workers for at least 5 years in Central Italy went from an amount equal to 19.2 units to a value equal to 20.3 units

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or equal to a value of 1 , 1 unit equal to 5.72%. Between 2015 and 2016 the value of the percentage of temporary contract workers for at least 5 years went from an amount equal to 20.3 units up to a value equal to 20.5 units equal to an amount of 0.2 units equal to 0.98%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017, the value of those employed in temporary work for at least 5 years decreased from a value of 20.5 units to a value of 17.4 units or equal to a value of -3.1 units equal to -15.12%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of those employed in temporary work for at least 5 years increased from an amount equal to 17.4 units up to a value of 18.5 units or equal to a value of 1.1 units equal to 6.32%. Between 2018 and 2019 the value of the amount of those employed in fixed-term contracts for at least 5 years decreased from a value of 18.5 units equal to 16.9 units or equal to a change of -1.6 units equal at a value of -8.6%. Between 2014 and 2019 the value of those employed in temporary work for at least 5 years decreased from a value of -2.3 units equal to a value of -11.9%.

The trend in the percentage of temporary contract workers for at least 5 years in Southern Italy. The value of temporary contract workers for at least 5 years in Southern Italy went from a value of 26.8% to a value of 25.1% in the transition between 2014 and 2015, i.e. equal to a change in -1.7 units equal to an amount of -6.3%. Between 2015 and 2016 the value of the percentage of temporary contract workers for at least 5 years decreased from an amount equal to 25.1 to a value equal to 24.6 units or equal to a value of -0.5 units equal to an amount of -1.99%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017, the value of fixed-term contract workers increased from an amount equal to 24.6 units up to a value equal to 24.8 units equal to a value of 0.2 units equal to a value of 0.813%. Between 2017 and 2018, the value of those employed in forward contracts for at least 5 years increased from a value of 24.8 units to a value of 24.9 units or equal to a change of 0.1 units equal to an amount of 0.4%. Between 2018 and 2019 the value of forward contracts for at least 5 years has decreased from an amount equal to 24.9 units up to a value of 23.5 units or equal to a value of -1.4 units equal to a variation of -5.6%. Between 2014 and 2019 the value of the amount of term contacts for 5 years in Southern Italy decreased by an amount equal to -3.3 units equal to a value of -12.3%.

Conclusions. In summary, we can underline that the value of forward contracts for 5 years has decreased in all Italian regions in the period between 2014 and 2019 except for some regions such as Abruzzo, Puglia, Liguria, and Molise which have therefore manifested the presence of a labor market characterized by growing insecurity. In all other regions, the amount of forward contracts for at least 5 years has decreased significantly. However, in a broad sense, the presence of forward contracts tends to be a decreasing element even in active regions such as, for example, Lombardy with -4.7%, Veneto with -3.8% and Emilia -Romagna with -2.1% between 2004 and 2019.

Declarations

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Occupati in lavori a termine da almeno 5 anni. Fonte: Istat-BES.

Rank	Regione	2019
1	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 31,8
2	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 25,9
3	<i>Calabria</i>	★ 23,7
4	<i>Molise</i>	★ 22,4
5	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	★ 21,8
6	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 21,3
7	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 21,1
8	<i>Lazio</i>	★ 20
9	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	★ 18
9	<i>Campania</i>	★ 18
10	<i>Liguria</i>	☆ 16,6
11	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	☆ 16,4
12	<i>Toscana</i>	☆ 14,5
13	<i>Sardegna</i>	☆ 14,4
14	<i>Umbria</i>	☆ 13,8
15	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	☆ 13,3
16	<i>Marche</i>	☆ 13,2
17	<i>Piemonte</i>	☆ 11,8
18	<i>Veneto</i>	☆ 10,7
19	<i>Lombardia</i>	☆ 9,9

